

FAMILY CONFLICTS AND THEIR CAUSES

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada oilaviy nizolarning mohiyati, ularning tasnifi va asosiy sabablariga ilmiy yondashuv asosida baho berilgan. Oilaviy ziddiyatlarning kelib chiqish omillari sifatida muloqot yetishmovchiligi, moliyaviy muammolar, shaxsiy manfaatlarning to‘qnashuvi, tarbiya uslublaridagi tafovutlar, qarindoshlar bilan bog‘liq muammolar va ishonchsizlik kabi jihatlar tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, oilaviy nizolarni oldini olish bo‘yicha samarali chora-tadbirlar taklif etilgan. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari oilaviy barqarorlikni mustahkamlashga qaratilgan ilmiy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so‘zlar: Oilaviy nizolar, oilaviy munosabatlar, nizolar sabablari, muloqot, moliyaviy muammolar, tarbiya, qarindoshlar bilan munosabat, ishonchsizlik.

Аннотация: В данной статье дана оценка сущности семейных конфликтов, их классификации и основных причин на основе научного подхода. В качестве факторов, способствующих возникновению семейных конфликтов, были проанализированы такие аспекты, как отсутствие общения, финансовые проблемы, конфликт личных интересов, различия в стилях воспитания, проблемы с родственниками и недоверие. Также были предложены эффективные меры по предотвращению семейных конфликтов. Результаты данного исследования имеют научное и практическое значение, направленное на укрепление стабильности семьи.

Ключевые слова: семейные конфликты, семейные отношения, причины конфликтов, общение, финансовые проблемы, воспитание, отношения с родственниками, недоверие.

Abstract: This article provides an assessment of the nature of family conflicts, their classification and the main causes based on a scientific approach. Such aspects as lack of communication, financial problems, conflict of personal interests, differences in parenting styles, problems with relatives and distrust were analyzed as factors contributing to the emergence of family conflicts. Effective measures to prevent family conflicts were also proposed. The results of this study have scientific and practical significance aimed at strengthening family stability.

Keywords: family conflicts, family relations, causes of conflicts, communication, financial problems, upbringing, relationships with relatives, distrust.

Family conflicts are an inevitable part of human existence, and understanding the causes and resolutions to these conflicts is a crucial issue for social scientists, particularly psychologists, sociologists, and legal experts. This article aims to analyze the primary causes of family disputes from a scientific perspective and explore ways to resolve them.

Today, spouses often maintain little in common. At the first sign of an unresolvable issue, they dissolve their union and seek another partner, without considering the possibility of a similar outcome occurring again. Based on statistics from marriages and divorces in the 21st century, it is disheartening to note that half of marriages end in separation due to a lack of communication and inability to address accumulated grievances.

The research of V. K. Myager and T. M. Mishina draws attention to the fact that conflict in families occurs when both parties try to occupy the same space, play different roles, and pursue different goals.

According to scientific research, family conflicts can arise due to several main factors:

Emotional causes of common family conflicts - Discontent in various areas. Such a psychological issue will not only have a negative impact on one partner, but will also create tension in the relationship and lead to intimate arguments. The need for attention and affection, exacerbated by problems in the intimate area between partners, inevitably leads to thoughts of separation and betrayal, which threatens a once-stable relationship. The psychological unwillingness of a couple to start a family is another significant factor. This does not depend on the age of the individuals, but rather on their sense of togetherness and ability to accept responsibility for another person. Marriage requires empathy for the other's interests and the ability to see things from their perspective. Failure to do so can lead to disagreements.

Lack of communication - The lack of effective communication between family members can lead to misunderstandings and conflict. It is important to express feelings clearly and listen to each other to avoid misunderstandings.

Financial issues - Financial problems can increase stress and lead to conflict. It's important to communicate about finances openly and work together to find solutions.

Differences in interests and values - When different family members have different interests or values, conflicts can arise. It's essential to respect each other's differences and find common ground.

Parenting styles - Different parenting approaches can cause conflicts between parents. It's helpful to discuss and agree on a common approach.

Relationship with in-laws - Difficulties in managing relationships with in-laws can also contribute to conflict. Communication and understanding are key to resolving these issues.

Separation of Work and Household Responsibilities - Improper Allocation of Household and Child Care Responsibilities Can Lead to Family Conflicts

Betrayal and Distrust - When Family Members' Trust in Each Other is Violated, It Seriously Affects Family Relationships and Increases the Likelihood of Divorce

Emotional and Physical Abuse - A physiological conflict. For example, partners have different biological cycles, such as one being a morning person and the other being a night owl. This can lead to conflict. Psychologists recommend addressing this type of conflict early on in a relationship, understanding each other's differences, and discussing them openly. This is the best way to prevent conflict from escalating. It is also important to create a living space that accommodates both partners' needs and desires. If conflict does occur, it is important to remember that it is not the end of the relationship. Instead, it can be an opportunity for growth and understanding. The best way to resolve conflict is through compromise.

Constructive conflicts involve the spouses' determination to resolve the disagreement, while destructive conflicts separate the partners from each other.

Another way to categorize family conflicts is based on their authenticity. Genuine conflicts arise due to objective reasons and are generally perceived by both parties appropriately. In contrast, false conflicts exist only in the subjective perception of one or both spouses.

Finally, conflicts can be categorized as explicit or hidden. Explicit conflicts are characterized by vivid emotional displays, outbursts of verbal and non-verbal aggression, while hidden conflicts are based on unspoken grievances, unwillingness to communicate, and secret confrontations that are difficult to identify and resolve.

Ways and means of resolving family conflicts

During the process of living together, couples may experience difficulties and conflicts. However, happiness is worth fighting for and requires effort and compromise in daily life. In order to maintain love and understanding in the home,

and to resolve all disagreements in a constructive manner, each partner must try their best.

The first and most important thing you need to do is to learn to be patient. In order to see your partner as yourself, you need to turn a blind eye to their shortcomings and try to become part of them. You should try to empathize with them, not ignore or dismiss their personality, but instead listen carefully and try to understand them. It is also important to be able to negotiate and compromise with your partner. Remember that there is always a way to improve the situation, no matter how difficult it may seem. If both partners are willing to work together to find a solution, and not blame each other for the problems, then they will surely succeed.

There are various psychological techniques that can be used to resolve family conflicts. Some of the most effective techniques include:

"I am" messages: Instead of blaming others during a conflict, express your feelings using "I" statements. For example, instead of saying "You always ignore me!", say "I feel ignored when you don't respond to me." This technique can help reduce tension and make it easier to communicate with others.

Active listening: When in conflict with a family member, listen to their point of view and try to understand how they feel. Ask questions and use phrases like "I hear what you're saying" and "I understand how you feel". This can help create a more understanding and respectful environment.

Taking a break: If the conflict becomes too heated, take a break from the situation and step away for a few minutes. Go for a walk, do something else, or just take some time to calm down. This can give you time to think more clearly about the issue and help prevent escalation.

The search for a compromise - During a conflict, instead of shouting "I have to win!" or "My opinion is right!" try to find a reasonable solution that benefits both

parties. Use the "swap places" technique and imagine yourself in the other person's position to increase empathy and reduce tension.

Managing emotions - It's important not to let emotions get the best of you during a conflict. Take deep breaths, meditate, or speak slowly to stay calm and keep a clear head.

Setting family rules - Creating and following pre-agreed family rules can help prevent recurring conflicts. For example, make monthly financial plans together or assign household responsibilities ahead of time.

In conclusion, in order to avoid family conflicts and eliminate them, it is important to establish effective communication in the family, strive to understand each other and form mutual respect. Also important is the use of psychological and legal approaches to conflict prevention, the development of social support systems. Ensuring family stability is an important factor in the development of society and requires a scientific approach to this issue.

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Семейные конфликты: причины, последствия, пути их разрешения.
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